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Strategic Importance of the Green Energy Zone in The Sustainable Development of the Karabakh Economic Region

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Abstract: The strategic importance of the creation and development of a green energy zone in the sustainable development of the Karabakh economic region is being examined. Azerbaijan is expanding its energy infrastructure in the context of sustainable development and is creating green energy zones for this purpose. The organization of green energy infrastructure is in the focus of special attention in the processes of revitalization of post-conflict areas. Hydroelectric power plants are being restored, modernized and new ones are being created. By attracting investments, a solar power infrastructure is being formed in the territory of the Jabrayil region with the participation of BP. A large number of transmission substations have been put into operation. The importance of green energy in the socio-economic development of the newly created Karabakh economic region is increasing. Measures to use green energy are a priority in the processes of returning former internally displaced persons to their homelands. Proposals have been made to develop green energy infrastructure and increase opportunities in the region.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh economic region, green energy, green energy infrastructure, solar energy, hydroelectric power plants.

Introduction

It should be noted that in modern times, Azerbaijan is experiencing a period of its own dynamic development as an independent state and has become a strong country where global initiatives are taking shape. Based on the initial results of COP29, we can note that it is possible to make serious contributions to solving complex problems that concern the peoples and states of the world. However, for this, it is important to unite the efforts of the world's states and use them effectively to take more effective measures (Aliyev, Sh.T., Babayev, F., Gafarli, G., Galandarova, U., Balajayeva, T., 2023). At COP29, the consolidation of the necessary financial resources required to eliminate the negative consequences of global climate change has gained strategic importance. The issues of establishing specialized institutions for climate finance, developing investment and financial mechanisms, and making commitments by states on green energy, especially commitments related to the maintenance of green energy, have become quite relevant. In this context, improving the country's energy policy is one of the important issues (Gasimli, V.A., Huseyn, R.Z., Huseynov, R.F., Hasanov, R. B., Jafarov, C. R., & Bayramova, A. B., 2022). There is a strong potential for renewable energy production in post-conflict areas, primarily in the Karabakh economic region (Samadzade, Z.A., 2022). According to various estimates, these areas have 10 gigawatts of solar and wind energy potential. In addition, the potential for using geothermal energy sources as "green energy" in the Shusha region is noteworthy (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2022). President Ilham Aliyev has declared a 10,000 square kilometer area in post-conflict areas, including Karabakh, a "green energy" zone. In this regard, the President of the country signed an Order "On measures to establish a "green energy" zone in the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated May 3, 2021. In accordance with this order, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan approved the "Action Plan on the establishment of a "green energy" zone in the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2022-2026". Currently, the implementation of this plan has entered an intensive phase and the processes of establishing green energy infrastructure in the region are intensifying.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The main purpose of writing the article is to show the strategic importance of green energy in the sustainable development of Karabakh. At the same time, the issues of forming a green economy, creating an efficient structure of the economy and improving existing economic mechanisms, based on ensuring the priority of green energy, are becoming increasingly relevant. Among such problems and issues, the need to solve the problems of economical and productive use of resource potential, and intensify the transfer of high technologies, especially waste-free technologies, is more noticeable. In this regard, there is a serious need for fundamental research, synthesis, comparison and generalization of such issues. In addition, there is a serious need to accelerate the establishment of the structure of green energy and ensure the efficiency of the mechanisms applied in this direction. In particular, it is important to take measures to intensify the socio-economic development of the Karabakh economic region and in accordance with the principles of sustainable development. In this regard, the problems and prospects of organizing green energy infrastructure in the region have been studied, and relevant proposals have been developed.

Research Results

It should be noted that the transformation taking place in the development processes of the global economy determines new trends and development impulses in modern conditions. The issues of

establishing green energy infrastructure are of exceptional importance, and in this regard, special attention is paid to the efficient use of energy resources, taking into account the need to create an appropriate infrastructure based on the basic principles of sustainable development (Ковальская, А.Э., 2023). Thus, the negative consequences of complex processes and global problems in ensuring the energy security of countries around the world are increasing. Problems in these areas are becoming more complex every year, and the negative consequences of climate change are increasing (Усков А.Е., Гиркин, А.С., Дауров, А.В., 2014). At the same time, there are difficulties in the rational distribution of energy resources, therefore, the task of ensuring the production and entry of green energy into the world market is of the highest priority (Сидорович, В., 2015).

We would also like to draw attention to the issues of forecasting world population growth by 2050. On the other hand, since energy resources are unevenly distributed between regions and countries of the world, additional difficulties, problems, conflicts, etc. arise. Against this background, energy security problems are rapidly increasing and diversification of energy sources is required. It is this factor that further conditions the intensification of the development of the green economy and, first of all, the creation of the necessary high-tech green energy infrastructure, which requires consistently large investments (Piana V., Aliyev, Sh.T. and etc., 2009). In our opinion, the countries of the world should make greater efforts and take necessary measures to solve global energy problems. Solving problems in this direction gives an additional impetus to the development of the country's economy (Əliyev, Ş.T., 2018). In addition, a competitive environment is created in the country and the potential for specialization in the international division of labor system increases (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2015). Ensuring energy security requires taking systematic measures (Aliyev, S., Gulaliyev, M., Purhani, S., Mehdiyeva, G., & Mustafayev, E., 2024). At the same time, it is important to take continuous measures in terms of the application of high technologies (Alguliyev, R.M., Aliyev A.G., Aliyev Sh.T., Shahverdiyeva, R.O., 2014). In many countries around the world, the creation of free economic zones creates additional opportunities for the development of individual economic sectors, including the development of energy infrastructure (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2008). On the other hand, a favorable environment is created for the implementation of economic development priorities in similar zones (Aliyev, Sh.T. (2010). In terms of economic efficiency, increasing the use of energy resources and creating additional sources are important conditions (Aliyev, Sh.T., 2014). It should be noted that the creation of more economical regimes (mechanisms) of using natural resources and non-renewable energy resources should be ensured. It is necessary to deepen the processes of transfer and application of high technologies between countries and to ensure the development of effective mechanisms for the efficient use of energy resources. We believe that despite the intensity of the creation and implementation of green energy infrastructure, the ecological situation in the world is deteriorating year by year. This factor clearly demonstrates the importance of the transition of countries of the world to a green economy and, in particular, to green energy. It is in the context of the above-mentioned problems that more intensive measures are being taken in most countries of the world to improve the concept of a green economy and create a green energy infrastructure.

In our opinion, against the background of these problems, factors arising from the concept of sustainable development come to the fore (Ələkbərov, U.K., 2017). First of all, the issues of economical use of resources, development and application of more efficient regulatory mechanisms and

incentives for existing mechanisms, taking into account the needs of future generations for these resources, have risen to a strategic level.

In the modern era, the issues of modernization of economic processes attract attention with their relevance (Gasimli, V.A., 2014). Currently, it is important to create appropriate high-tech energy infrastructure in the reconstruction of post-conflict areas in Azerbaijan (Quliyev, E.A., 2023). Intensive development of green energy infrastructure also acts as one of the main components of building a green economy (Gurbanov, S.H., 2022). At the same time, the demand for energy resources is increasing in the processes of sustainable development of industrial sectors in modern times (Megits, N., Aliyev, S.T., Pustovhar, S., Bielialov, T., Prokopenko, O. 2022). Yaşıl enerji enerji və yaşıl iqtisadiyyat problemlərinin sistemli şəkildə həll edilməsi, həm də ölkənin davamlı inkişafına təkan verən amillərdəndir (Muradov, A.J., Hajiyev, N.O., 2014). In addition, there is a tendency for countries around the world to seek alternative ways to ensure energy security. In this case, bringing the problems of greening and efficiency of the economy to the agenda, conducting in-depth scientific research towards the creation and application of new progressive models of the economic regime is considered an inevitable process. At the same time, achieving the effective application of the results of scientific research in various segments of the economy is of great importance (Алиев Ш.Т., 2014). All of this is of great importance in terms of the country's economic security (Алиев, Ш.Т., 2020).

It should be noted that in the context of increasing economic demand in the modern era, the productive use of green energy sources is of great importance. In recent decades, humanity has increasingly realized that the burning of fossil fuels such as coal, oil and natural gas has led to large-scale global problems that have become unmanageable. We have specifically distinguished a group of issues related to these: 1) Modern energy sources are obtained from depleted natural resources. It is understood that in the relatively near future there will be a shortage of natural resources, as a result of which future generations will face difficulties in energy production and ensuring the viability of the population. 2) As a result of the active development of energy, the problem of environmental pollution is becoming even more acute. However, green energy minimizes the damage to the environment and thereby reduces the negative consequences of the global problem. 3) The cost of current non-renewable energy resources is constantly changing, creating difficulties in the world and the global economy. However, green energy can help maintain stable prices, because after the initial costs associated with the creation of a renewable energy source, the costs of maintaining and operating this source are often lower than those of using fossil fuels.

One of the complex issues in resolving the existing problems in the Karabakh economic region is ensuring the sustainable development of post-conflict areas (Алиев, Ш.Т., Меликова, Л.А., 2022). However, some experts believe that the intensive development of Karabakh should be considered as a new driver of economic growth for Azerbaijan (Гасымлы, В., 2022). In addition, the creation of green energy infrastructures in post-conflict areas will play an important role in the development of these areas (Əliyev, Ş., 2020).

On the other hand, green energy can act as a catalyst for energy security, sustainable development, and social, technological, and industrial innovation in a country. Increasing green energy consumption has a positive impact on its economic and social development (Ташкеева, Е.Е., 2020). Moreover, since energy plays a significant role in industrial and technological development, the supply and use of cheap, clean fuel is of particular importance for global stability in the world. In this regard, there is a need to use renewable energy sources that can positively affect all spheres of life, including the stable development of national economies. In our opinion, the development of green energy in the

economic sphere can have a positive impact on solving a group of issues: 1. Increasing the number of jobs and alleviating the employment problem. 2. Reducing consumer spending and creating more resources. 3. Eliminating dependence on fossil fuels imported from other countries and 4. Green energy is not only a solution to global problems, but also a means of stimulating the economic activity of entrepreneurs, business entities and the population (Ramil, H., 2022). At the same time, we believe that it makes sense to create an environmentally friendly, i.e. green energy potential that will help solve the problem of environmental pollution. These facts help stimulate sales and consumption. "Until a green energy source is created that can fully meet the demand for electricity, even if humanity realizes that it causes irreparable damage to the environment, it will not be able to stop burning fossil fuels" (Худотеплова, К.И., 2022). Currently, researchers and experts are increasingly engaged in the study and development of mechanisms for the formation of new clean and sustainable energy sources, which means that fossil fuels will soon be replaced by more environmentally friendly resources.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2050. In addition, it is planned to increase the share of renewable energy in the structure of total energy resources to 30% by 2030. Azerbaijan has made serious and long-term commitments to implement the necessary measures to ensure a 1.5°C temperature limit in the global context. Azerbaijan is implementing constant and consistent measures in these conceptual directions (Azərbaycan Respublikasında 2024-cü ilin "Yaşıl dünya naminə həmrəylik ili" elan edilməsi haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Sərəncam, 2023).

In addition, Azerbaijan plans to increase the volume of natural gas exported to the European market to 20 billion m³ by 2027. At the same time, the creation of infrastructure for alternative energy sources has begun in various regions of the country. In 2037, 6 GW of renewable energy can be produced. Renewable energy capacity in Azerbaijan is 135 GW onshore and 157 GW offshore. The UAE's Masdar company has commissioned a 230 MW solar power plant. Saudi Arabia's Acwa Power is currently building a 240 MW wind power plant. Within the framework of COP29, an agreement was signed with the United Kingdom's BP company on the construction of a 240 MW solar power plant in the Jabrayil region. Thanks to this project, decarbonization will be ensured at the Sangachal terminal, one of the largest oil and gas terminals in the world. The opportunity to export green energy to Europe is emerging.

It is commendable that in post-conflict areas, including the Karabakh economic region, the electricity demand is 100 percent covered by "green energy". At the same time, taking into account promising green energy projects, the total capacity of "green energy" projects implemented and expected to be implemented in the liberated regions is estimated at 1,100 MW. Serious measures are already being taken to supply Shusha city with electricity, and new, high-quality power lines have been put into operation. An electric substation has been built to provide the city with stable electricity. In order to connect Shusha city to the general energy system of Azerbaijan and provide the city with reliable, stable and uninterrupted electricity, the construction of the 110-kilovolt "Shukurbayli-Shusha" overhead power transmission line, starting from the "Shusha" substation and the "Shukurbayli" substation in the Fuzuli region, is continuing rapidly at a distance of 75 kilometers. It should be noted that the potential of wind energy in the mountainous areas of Karabakh is 300-500 megawatts. Work is underway to attract foreign investors to "green energy" projects, and the Japanese company "Tepsco" has been involved in these processes.

In general, we can note that the processes of revitalization of post-conflict territories are related to the formation of a green economy structure and the creation of green energy infrastructure. "The newly

created Karabakh economic regions have great resources in terms of forming and increasing green energy potential" (Aliyev, Sh.T., 2021). Development projects for the Karabakh economic region mainly cover priorities until 2040. In particular, taking into account the current issues arising from the tasks of the First State Program on the return of internally displaced persons to their homelands, the prospects for the formation and increase of green energy potential in these economic regions are becoming increasingly attractive. The liberated territories have been declared a green energy zone in general and a targeted action program has been formulated in this regard.

Conclusions

Taking into account the near and far perspectives, we would like to highlight a group of issues and factors for intensifying the processes of creating green energy infrastructure in order to ensure the sustainable development of the Karabakh economic region:

- In the context of global challenges and sustainable development, the strong potential of the Karabakh economic region in ensuring the transition to green energy in Azerbaijan is noteworthy;
- The scale of investment projects launched to create green energy infrastructure in the Karabakh economic region is expanding and specific projects are already being implemented;
- There is a need for a thorough study of the green energy potential of the Karabakh economic region, optimal assessment of resources and related reserves;
- In intensifying the processes of creating green energy infrastructure in the region, public-private sector cooperation should be given wide scope and the direction of private investments in this area should be maximally stimulated, etc.

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